

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet
hash://md5/b25e91ce4df87deb97380933ef341225

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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet, has fingerprint hash://md5/b25e91ce4df87deb97380933ef341225, is 1.24MiB in size and contains 92,822 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eatenBy) between 52 primary taxa (e.g., *Peromyscus maniculatus* (Wagner, 1845)) and 9 associated taxa (e.g., Burrowing Owl). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Frier D (2020): Royal Saskatchewan Museum - Owl Pellet Collection. v2.1. Royal Saskatchewan Museum. Dataset/Occurrence. <https://doi.org/10.5886/f0xsbu> <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet/archive/ae69a4b244f9d2e050b656ea4240f791c72299a3.zip> 2026-01-24T05:52:45.373Z hash://md5/b25e91ce4df87deb97380933ef341225

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.1
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 1.24MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet`, has fingerprint hash://md5/b25e91ce4df87deb97380933ef341225, is 1.24MiB in size and contains 92,822 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., `eatenBy`) between 52 primary taxa (e.g., *Peromyscus maniculatus* (Wagner, 1845)) and 9 associated taxa (e.g., Burrowing Owl).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Lasiurus cinereus (Palisot de Beauvois, 1796)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	urn:catalog:RSKM:OWLPELLET:OP-1.0001
Lasiurus cinereus (Palisot de Beauvois, 1796)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	urn:catalog:RSKM:OWLPELLET:OP-1.0002

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Lemmiscus curtatus (Cope, 1868)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	urn:catalog:RSKM:OWLPellet:OP- 1.0003
Lemmiscus curtatus (Cope, 1868)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	urn:catalog:RSKM:OWLPellet:OP- 1.0004

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eatenBy	92822

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Peromyscus maniculatus (Wagner, 1845)	48138
Microtus pennsylvanicus (Ord, 1815)	16255
Lemmiscus curtatus (Cope, 1868)	8383
Aves	3323
Sorex Linnaeus, 1758	2811
Onychomys leucogaster (Wied-Neuwied, 1841)	2374
Anura	2210
Perognathus fasciatus Wied-Neuwied, 1839	2161
Mus musculus Linnaeus, 1758	1177
Thomomys talpoides (Richardson, 1828)	866
Sorex haydeni Baird, 1857	862
Urodela	839
Spea bombifrons (Cope, 1863)	762
Uroditellus richardsonii (Sabine, 1822)	465
Pseudacris maculata (Agassiz, 1850)	234
Rattus norvegicus (Berkenhout, 1769)	210
Chiroptera	201
Sorex cinereus Kerr, 1792	164
Sylvilagus nuttallii (Bachman, 1837)	130

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Burrowing Owl	54746
Great Horned Owl	37560
owl	219
Northern Hawk Owl	142
Long-eared Owl	77
Short-eared Owl	25
Snowy Owl	24
Snowy OWL	24
Northern Saw-Whet Owl	5

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Peromyscus maniculatus (Wagner, 1845)	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	26779
Peromyscus maniculatus (Wagner, 1845)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	21035
Microtus pennsylvanicus (Ord, 1815)	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	9502
Microtus pennsylvanicus (Ord, 1815)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	6660
Lemmiscus curtatus (Cope, 1868)	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	6058
Aves	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	2955
Lemmiscus curtatus (Cope, 1868)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	2289
Anura	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	2123
Onychomys leucogaster (Wied-Neuwied, 1841)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	1753

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Sorex Linnaeus, 1758	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	1604
Perognathus fasciatus Wied-Neuwied, 1839	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	1207
Sorex Linnaeus, 1758	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	1202
Mus musculus Linnaeus, 1758	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	967
Perognathus fasciatus Wied-Neuwied, 1839	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	949
Spea bombifrons (Cope, 1863)	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	649
Urodela	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	623
Sorex haydeni Baird, 1857	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	622
Onychomys leucogaster (Wied-Neuwied, 1841)	eatenBy	Burrowing Owl	618
Thomomys talpoides (Richardson, 1828)	eatenBy	Great Horned Owl	616

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download [svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Burrowing	NONE	col	Burrowing
Great	NONE	col	Great
Aves	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Aves
Anaxyrus hemiophrys	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Anaxyrus hemiophrys

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	9
col	class	2
col	family	1
col	genus	6
col	order	3
col	species	38
col	subgenus	1
discoverlife	NA	58
gbif	NA	9
gbif	class	2
gbif	family	2
gbif	genus	8
gbif	order	3
gbif	species	38
itis	NA	9
itis	class	1
itis	family	1
itis	genus	5
itis	order	4
itis	species	38
mdd	NA	58
ncbi	NA	9
ncbi	class	1
ncbi	family	1
ncbi	genus	5
ncbi	order	4
ncbi	species	38
pbdb	NA	15
pbdb	class	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	family	2
pbdb	genus	5
pbdb	order	3
pbdb	species	32
tpt	NA	19
tpt	family	1
tpt	genus	4
tpt	order	1
tpt	species	33
wfo	NA	57
wfo	genus	1
worms	NA	37
worms	class	1
worms	family	1
worms	genus	5
worms	order	3
worms	species	12

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	12
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	48
col	SYNONYM_OF	5
discoverlife	NONE	61
gbif	NONE	12
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	54
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	11
itis	NONE	12
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	47
itis	SYNONYM_OF	3
mdd	NONE	30
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	31
ncbi	NONE	12
ncbi	SAME_AS	47
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	2

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
pbdb	NONE	18
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	43
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	12
tpt	NONE	22
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	39
wfo	NONE	60
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1
worms	NONE	40
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	21
worms	SYNONYM_OF	3

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T00:44:29Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-01-28T00:44:29Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-01-28T00:44:35Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/rskm-owlpellet/archive/ae69a4b244f9d2e050b656ea4240f791c792822 interaction(s)
2026-01-28T00:44:35Z	summary	92822 interaction(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder	2

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-28) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

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Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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